

Localisation and monitoring grazing cows using computer vision

Writer: Jérémie Haumont & Jarissa Maselyne

Organisation: ILVO

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Introduction

In pasture-based livestock production one of the major challenges is ensuring adequate feed intake to avoid malnutrition and hunger. However, feed quantity and quality vary considerably throughout a pasture and over time. Therefore, information about when and where the animals are grazing can contribute to improved management decisions and can also help to detect potential health issues. In barns IoT sensors and precision livestock farming (PLF) technologies are increasingly adopted to monitor the animals. For example, animals can be equipped with radio frequency identification (RFID) tags to identify them at the feeding bunk, drinking station or in the milking robot. Accelerometers are also widely used to monitor the behaviour, detect diseases and oestrus [1]. But there is a significant divide between technological innovations for indoors and on the pasture.

For outdoor positioning GPS collars can be used. Despite the ability to track animals over a large area, the sensors are mainly limited by the battery life and data transmission frequency [2]. Transferring the use of accelerometers to an outdoor system can cause reliability issues as animals feeding indoors are standing still at the feeding bunk while on a pasture the natural behaviour is to walk slowly forward [3]. Recently, computer vision gained increasing attention to solve multiple challenges of livestock monitoring simultaneously such as identification, behaviour analysis, and welfare assessment [4]. And it offers also great potential for outdoor application with the rise of edge computing and fast mobile network connectivity for data transfer [5].

Vision-based outdoor localisation

In the past decade there has been a tremendous increase in the application of artificial intelligence (AI) to solve computer vision problems. And the latest state-of-the-art models can be used for object detection, keypoint detection or pose estimation, and segmentation with great accuracy [6]. Therefore, a mobile camera setup with edge computing capabilities is being developed as versatile tool to localize cows in the pasture and monitor their behaviour.

The setup is equipped with an industrial USB-camera, with a 4mm lens and with a resolution of (2048 x 1536), which can be installed on a mobile pole at 6 meter high at the border of the pasture. This allows to monitor animals on an area of about one hectare. A combination of other imaging sensors and lenses can be used to vary the monitoring area. The images will be processed on the extreme edge as transferring the continuous stream of 3 mega pixel images at 30 frames per second requires a huge data throughput which will lead to an expensive solution. However, the computation power of edge devices is often limited compared to cloud solutions, which might impact model accuracy.

For the detection of the cows the latest version (v8) of the YOLO (You Only Look Once) model will be used as it offers built-in functionalities for object detection, pose estimation, segmentation and tracking. Additionally, the model is available in multiple sizes, i.e. number of parameters, (nano, small, medium, large, and extra-large) that have a difference in computational load but there will be an effect on the model accuracy. The model will be deployed on a Nvidia Jetson Orin Nano due to its great

balance between computation power and energy consumption. The medium-sized YOLOv8 model can be executed at about 40 FPS with a latency of 25ms while only consuming 15W [7]. There are several tools that could be used to even further decrease inference time such as using quantization and compiling the model into optimized formats such as TensorRT [8].

Finally, the system should convert each detection of a cow to a GPS coordinate to be able to extract the exact position. However, a single RGB camera has no inherent capacity to sense 3D information of its environment. To alleviate this issue a two-stage approach was developed:

1. Due to optical characteristics of the camera and lens the captured images get distorted, meaning that a straight line in reality does not remain straight in the image. These effects can be removed by calibrating these intrinsic camera parameters using a checkerboard with known dimensions.
2. In an ideal situation the pasture is observed from a position perpendicular to the surface, however this would limit the coverage. Therefore, the camera is tilted to optimize the field of view. Using a projective transformation of the tilted image the position of known landmarks can be linked to the corresponding image coordinates (Figure 1). And this allows to estimate the GPS coordinates of detected animals throughout the pasture.

Figure 1 (Left) Grazing cows detected by the YoloV8 model and (right) the detection converted to GPS coordinates.

Future developments

The first phase of the development focussed on the detection and subsequently localisation of the cows in the pasture. In the next steps the detection algorithm will be extended to additionally distinguish between different behaviours such as grazing, lying, walking and standing. Furthermore, a tracking algorithm will also be implemented to capture the information of individual cows. This system could also be integrated with remote sensing techniques that enable to monitor the spatial variation in sward quality and quantity. Combination of these information sources could assist farmers in improving their feed management and contribute to increasing animal health and welfare.

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